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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
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THE MAJORITY RULE AND MINORITY PROTECTION UNDER THE COMPANIES AND ALLIED MATTERS ACT, 2020

By

Barau Isah Habila,¹ Muhammad Tahir Umar,² Ahmed Musa Fili³

Abstract

The decision of the court in the celebrated case of Salomon V. Salomon on corporate personality has many consequences. One of the effects of the decision is that companies are governed by the principle of majority rule. That is, corporate decisions are taken by the shareholders with a majority of the voting shares in a company. This Principle of majority rule was reaffirmed in the locus classicus case of Foss vs. Harbottle. Thus, a company acts through its constitutional organs, which are the Board of Directors and the General Members Meeting. However, over the years, exceptions to this general principle have evolved in various jurisdictions including Nigeria. This paper, therefore, examines the origin of the principles of majority rule. The paper also discusses the exceptions to the rule, which were developed to protect minority under the Nigerian company law. This is intended to ascertain whether the law has made enough protection for minority shareholders in the face of majority rule and whether such protections are adequate, realistic, practically realizable, and enforceable. The doctrinal method was deployed in conducting this research, where statutes, books, and case laws were reviewed. Part of the findings in the paper were the absence of effective inspection of corporate entities by the Corporate Affairs Commission, and the paper recommends that the requirements for leave of court before undertaking a derivative action are stringent and the Companies and Allied Matters Act should therefore be amended to expunge the requirement for leave. In addition, it is further recommended that an administrative procedure for filing a petition to the Corporate Affairs Commission before approaching the court should be put in place. This will be faster and reduce litigation.

Keyword: Majority rule, Minority Protection, CAMA, Company

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1.0 Introduction

The Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 2020 aims to balance the majority rule with minority protection in corporate governance. However, a pressing issue arises when the majority's decisions potentially harm the minority's interests, leading to unfair prejudice and oppression.

The majority rule, as enshrined in the *Foss v. Harbottle* rule, can lead to the tyranny of the majority, where the rights of minority shareholders are disregarded. This raises concerns about the protection of minority shareholders' interests, particularly in situations where the majority engages in oppressive or unfair conduct.

The basic principle governing the operation of a company can best be described as corporate democracy in that majority must prevail. This means that the majority must always have their way. Any decision regarding the affairs of the company and issues affecting the welfare of the shareholders are ordinarily supposed to be taken at a general meeting in a democratic manner. However, to ensure that this power of the majority is placed within reasonable bounds and does not result in the oppression of the minority and mismanagement of the company, the law provides for instances where the minority can either to protect the company or interest of the minorities, institute an action on behalf and in the name of a company. To appreciate these two important principles of corporate law, it is necessary to highlight the facts and decisions of the Court in the case of *Foss v. Harbottle* and *Edwards Vs. Halliwell*.

2.0 Provisions of the Companies and Allied Matters Act on the Principles of Majority Rule and The Exceptions to the Rule

In Nigeria, the common law principles of majority and the various exceptions to the Rule has been codified in the principal legislation governing corporate practice, the Companies and Allied Matters Act, (CAMA) 2020. CAMA provides that where an irregularity is made in the course of a company's affairs or any wrong is done to the company, only the company can sue to remedy that wrong and only the company can ratify the irregular conduct.⁴ This means that only the company may sue for wrong or ratify irregular conduct. The Act however, provided exceptions to this general principle thereby providing protection to minority shareholders. On this principle, Bello C.J.N

⁴ Section 341 of the CAMA

in *Omisade v. Akande*⁵ (observing Lord Denning MR in *Wallersteiner v. Moir*) has this to say:

Suppose the company is defrauded by insiders/ by directors who control/hold a majority of the shares, who can sue...? Those directors are themselves the wrongdoers ... they will not authorise the proceedings to be taken against themselves if a general meeting is called, they will vote down any suggestion that the company should sue”. Minority protection is where the law allows the minority holders to enforce certain rights in certain instances which can be termed “exceptions to the rule in *Foss V Harbottle*. This is because the majority in control may constitute an unruly horse if not checked.

CAMA provides that the Court, on the application of any member, may by injunction or declaration restrain the company or its officers from⁶:

- (a) entering into any transaction which is illegal or ultra vires;
- (b) purporting to do by ordinary resolution any act which by its articles or this Act required to be done by special resolution;
- (c) any act or omission affecting the applicant’s individual rights as a member;
- (d) committing fraud on either the company or the minority shareholders where the directors fail to take appropriate action to redress the wrong done;
- (e) where a company meeting cannot be called in time to be of practical use in redressing a wrong done to the company or to minority shareholders;
- (f) where the directors are likely to derive a profit or benefit, or have profited or benefited from their negligence or from their breach of duty; and
- (g) any other act or omission, where the interest of justice so demands.

Following from the above, it is worth pointing out that a member can institute a personal action to enforce a right due to him personally, or a representative action on behalf of himself and other affected members to enforce any right due to them.⁷ A member in this context includes the personal representative of a deceased member

⁵ (1987) 2 NWLR pt. 55 155 @170

⁶ Section 343 of the CAMA

⁷ Section 344 (1) of the CAMA

and any person to whom shares have been transferred or transmitted by operation⁸. The reliefs available to a member commencing a personal or representative action includes damages for any loss incurred on account of the breach of that right or declaration or injunction to restrain the company or the directors from doing a particular act⁹.

In the case of *Nigerian Stores Workers Union v. Uzor*¹⁰, it was decided that the rule in *Foss v. Harbottle* does not apply to ultra vires acts. Any individual or minority shareholders can therefore, sue to restrain any ultra-vires as for instance, a plan to misapply the funds of the company contrary to the provision of its memorandum. Also, *Benson Oduduro & Another v. National Union of Hotel and Personal Service Workers & Others*¹¹ where a resolution was passed which was ultra vires of the Trade Union's constitution, the court held that the plaintiffs were entitled to sue in spite of the fact that they participated in the meeting at which the resolution was passed. Furthermore, in the case of *Mbere v. Ofili*¹², Kazeem J. observed that the rule in *Foss v. Harbottle* does not prevent an individual member from suing, if the irregular act in respect of which he is using is one which could validly be done or sanctioned not by a simple majority of the members of the associations, but only by some special majority.

In addition to instituting action involving personal right, an applicant may apply to the Court for leave to bring an action in the name or on behalf of a company or a company's subsidiary, or to intervene in an action to which the company or the company's subsidiary is a party, for the purpose of prosecuting, defending or discontinuing the action on behalf of the company or the company's subsidiary¹³. This is also known as Derivative Action. However, before such an action is entertained by the Court, the applicant must establish the following¹⁴:

i. a cause of action has arisen from an actual or proposed act or omission involving negligence, default, breach of duty or trust by a director or a former director of the company;

⁸ Section 345 of the CAMA

⁹ Section 344 (2) of the CAMA

¹⁰ 9 (1971) 2 N.C.L.R 412

¹¹ Unreported suit No FCA/L/226/83, FCA decision

¹² (1968) 1 A.L.R Comm. 235

¹³ Section 346 (1) of the CAMA

¹⁴ Section 346 (2) of the CAMA

- ii. the applicant has given reasonable notice to the directors of the company of his intention to apply to the Court;
- iii. the directors of the company do not bring, diligently prosecute, defend or discontinue the action;
- iv. the notice contains a factual basis for the claim and the actual or potential damage caused to the company;
- v. the applicant is acting in good faith; and
- vi. it appears to be in the best interest of the company that the action be brought, prosecuted, defended or discontinued.

Upon being satisfied, the court may make an order:

- (a) authorising the applicant or any other person to control the conduct of the action;
- (b) giving directions for the conduct of the action;
- (c) directing that any amount adjudged payable by a defendant in the action is paid, in whole or in part, directly to former and present security holders of the company instead of to the company; and
- (d) requiring the company to pay reasonable legal fees incurred by the applicant in connection with the proceedings.

It is worth pointing out that apart from the general exceptions to the application of the principle in *Foss v. Harbottle*, CAMA has accorded additional protections to minority shareholders. These additional protections are discussed below:

i. Relief on the Grounds of Unfairly Prejudicial and Oppressive Conduct

Where the affairs of a company are conducted in an illegal or oppressive manner, an applicant can apply to the court for relief by way of petition for an order¹⁵. An applicant within this context includes a member of the company, a director or officer, former director or officer of the company, a creditor, the Commission and any other person who, in the discretion of the Court, is the proper person to make an application under section 354¹⁶. If the Court is satisfied that a petition under sections 353 and 354 is well

¹⁵ Section 354(1) of the CAMA

¹⁶ Section 353(1) of the CAMA

founded, it may make such order or orders as it deems fit for giving relief in respect of the matter complained of¹⁷. Upon being satisfied, the Court may make an order:

- a) that the company be wound up;
- b) for regulating the conduct of the affairs of the company in future;
- c) for the purchase of the shares of any member by other members of the company;
- d) for the purchase of the shares of any member by the company and for the reduction accordingly of the company's capital;
- e) directing the company to institute, prosecute, defend or discontinue specific proceedings, or authorising a member or the company to institute, prosecute, defend or discontinue specific proceedings in the name or on behalf of the company;
- f) varying or setting aside a transaction or contract to which the company is a party and compensating the company or any other party to the transaction or contract;
- g) directing an investigation to be made by the Commission;
- h) appointing a receiver or a receiver and manager of property of the company;
- i) restraining a person from engaging in specific conduct or from doing a specific act or thing; or
- j) requiring a person to do a specific act or thing.

ii. **Investigation of the Affairs of the Company:**

The Commission may appoint one or more competent inspectors to investigate the affairs of a company and to report on them in such manner as it may direct¹⁸. The appointment may be made in the case of a company having a share capital, on the application of members holding at least one-tenth of the class of shares issued, in the

¹⁷ . 355(1) of the CAMA 2020

¹⁸ Section 357 (1) of the CAMA

case of a company not having a share capital, on the application of at least one-tenth in number of the persons on the company.

iii. **Major Asset transaction**

Where a company intends to make purchase or other acquisition outside the usual course of the company's business, sale or other and transfer outside the usual course of the company's business, of the company's property or other rights the value of which, on the date of the company's decision to complete the transaction, is 50% or more of the book value of the company's assets based on the company's most recently compiled balance sheet, such must be referred to the General meeting for approval by special resolution¹⁹.

iv. **Right of Dissenting Shareholder(s) under Arrangement and Compromise**

Where under a contract, shares in a company are transferred to another company or its nominee, and those shares together with any other shares in the first mentioned company held by, or by a nominee for the transferee company or its subsidiary at the date of the transfer comprise or include nine-tenth in value of the shares in the first mentioned company or of a class of those shares, the transferee company shall, within one month from the date of the transfer give notice of that fact in the prescribed manner to the holder of the remaining shares or of the remaining shares of that class, as the case may be, who have not assented to the scheme or contract. A holder may, within three months from the giving of the notice to him, require the transferee company to acquire the shares in question. If a shareholder gives notice with respect to any share, the transferee company is entitled and bound to acquire those shares on the terms on under which the scheme or contract the shares of the approving shareholders were transferred to it, or on such other terms as may be agreed on as the Court hearing the application of either the transferee company or the shareholder deems fit²⁰.

3.0 CONCLUSION

It is no doubt that the principle of majority rule is a democratic corporate rule which seeks to maintain equilibrium amongst shareholders in terms of their varying

¹⁹ Section 342 of the CAMA

²⁰ Section 713 of the CAMA 2020

shareholding strength. However, the absolute and generous given to the majority in the administration of companies have been put under check. The court can interfere where the circumstance warrants. However, the realization of some of the protections accorded to the minorities may be challenging. This is based on the slow pace associated with the judicial system.

4.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the foregoing, we observed that the requirements to be fulfilled before undertaking a derivative action are stringent, particularly concerning obtaining leave of court.

Companies and Allied Matters Act should therefore be amended to expunge the requirement for leave. In addition, we recommend that an administrative procedure for filing a petition to the regulator (CAC) before approaching the court should be put in place. This will be faster and reduce litigation.